

A Dense and Highly Sophisticated Take on Global Economics
Amazon Book Review Series of “*Better Economics for the Earth*”

Chris B

January 16, 2025

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Better Economics for the Earth is a book of dazzling insight. Definitely a challenging read at times, and not nearly as accessible as your average economics-as-entertainment page turner, but an important one nonetheless. The thesis is one most of us are already well aware of: The first world economies and their obsession with continual growth is by definition unsustainable- financially, as well as environmentally. From there, authors Quan-Hoang Vuong and Minh-Hoang Nguyen make an utterly convincing case for a new definition of "value." Sound dense? It is. But it's also a mind-opener, for anybody who is studying macroeconomics in the modern climate-changing, AI-dominated era.

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Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Chris [1]. Reviewed in the United States on January 16, 2025.

(*) Note: This paper reprints Chris’s review [1] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [2]. The review’s title is generated based on the evaluation’s content.

References

[1] Chris, B. (2025, Jan. 16). A dense and highly sophisticated take on global economics. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2W6WFR08R23RN/>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>